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PARCEL SERVICE EMPLOYEES SATISFACTION TOWARDS HRM AND ORGANISATION FACTORS (A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ABT AND ARC PARCEL SERVICE COMPANY, COIMBATORE)

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Abstract

Recently employees working in the transportation service sector have been facing issues like: heavy work load, deadline, slim down employee benefits etc. Additionally, the safety concerns faced by female employees were important. Moreover, transportation employee like driver faces issues such as increasing fuel cost, unpleasant road conditions and increasing vehicle maintenance cost. On the other hand office level employees'/administrative employees' dissatisfaction towards their job has been notified as lack of career path development that in turn strongly influences their attrition rates from the transportation service sector. Though, the employees in these sectors are better educated and more qualified than ever before, they cannot raise their voice for their welfare/benefits. Since, transportation sector is highly centralized within trucking companies that leads to unpleasant working environment. These issues could be considered as the prime reasons for high rate of employee turnover. At this juncture it is advisable to assess employees' satisfaction towards HRM policies and Organisation factors and its influences on their intention of turnover. The study findings indicated that majority of the employees surveyed at both ABT and ARC were observed to least satisfied with both HR policies and organisation factors adhered in their organisation. The study further reveals that employees turn over intention is close linked with their dissatisfaction towards: organisation and personal fit, remuneration and recognition system, working environment and poor organisation commitment. Thus, it is suggested to the ABT and ARC parcel service companies to adopt strategic recruitment practices of finding right man for right job and always aim to pay them adequate salary and other perks. These organisations are also suggested to adhere very employee friendly work environment in order to enhance their level of satisfaction and to retain them as committed employees.

Key words: Parcel services, Employee satisfaction, HRM, Coimbatore

Introduction

In the past transportation service companies have been successful in attracting skilled workforce and have sufficient staff to manage their businesses effectively due to the effective use of the cultural richness of its workforce. Compared to other industries, the transportation and logistics industry has increased the rate of female employees across all functions and hierarchy levels more strongly. On the other hand, employees prefer to work in small and medium-sized transportation companies. In the past employees of transportation service sector had been remaining longer with their employers as compared with other industries. As these service companies perfectly align

the personal and career objectives of their entire management staff with overall corporate strategy. Compared to other sectors, it's more desirable to work in the transportation and logistics industry.

But, recently employees working in the transportation service sector have been facing issues like: heavy work load, deadline, slim down employee benefits etc. Additionally, the safety concerns faced by female employees were important. Moreover, transportation employee like driver faces issues such as increasing fuel cost, unpleasant road conditions and increasing vehicle maintenance cost. On the other hand office level employees'/administrative employees' dissatisfaction towards their job has been notified as lack of career path development that in turn strongly influences their attrition rates from the transportation service sector. Though, the employees in these sectors are better educated and more qualified than ever before, they cannot raise their voice for their welfare/benefits. Since, transportation sector is highly centralized within trucking companies that leads to unpleasant working environment. These issues could be considered as the prime reasons for high rate of employee turnover. At this juncture it is advisable to assess the employees feel of job satisfaction and address the issues currently faced by the transport service organisation like parcel service companies in order to retain the existing work force.

Statement of Problem

Human Resource Management (HRM) is considered a critical organisational resource that helps an organisation sustain its effectiveness. It is one important area that influences a number of employees' attitudes and behavior such as intent to leave, levels of job satisfaction, and organisational commitment. On the other side of the coin the workplace environment that is set in place impacts employee morale, productivity and engagement, both positively and negatively. It is generally believed that if employees are satisfied with their job would perform their duties well and will act committed to their job, and subsequently to their organisation. Thus, it is of utmost importance for employers to identify the factors that affect their employees' job satisfaction level since it would affect the performance of the organisation as well the performance of individual employees. Realising this fact this study aims to analyse the parcel service employees' level of satisfaction towards organisation and HR factors that are part of this organisation system.

Objective of the Study

This study aims to draw a link between the employees' satisfaction towards HRM policies and organisation factors and its influences on their intention of turnover.

Hypotheses of the Study

- H₀: Employees length of services significantly influences their satisfaction towards HR policies adhered in the parcel service companies i.e., ABT and ARC.
- H₀: Employees Cadre of Job significantly influences their satisfaction towards HR policies adhered in the parcel service companies i.e., ABT and ARC.
- H₀: Employees level of satisfaction towards their organisation's HR policies significantly influences their turn over intention in ABT and ARC parcel Service Company.
- H₀: Employees level of satisfaction towards the organisation factors significantly influences their turn over intention in ABT and ARC parcel Service Company.

Methodology and Material

The current study is both explorative and descriptive in nature. Study is based on the surface transportation (parcel services) services operating in Tamil Nadu. The study is based on the primary data and secondary data. The study applied judgmental and conveniences sampling techniques for selection of the sample. The researcher has adopted judgmental sampling technique for defining the entire population of surface transport operators (parcel

service operators) throughout Tamil Nadu. And researcher also applied convenience sampling techniques for the collection of primary data. It was observed that out of 205 surface transportation i.e., parcel services companies /firms operating in Coimbatore city, only two companies have more regional offices both at Coimbatore district level and also operates throughout Tamil Nadu i.e., ABT and ARC. ABT has 26 offices at Coimbatore city and ARC has 22 offices operating across Coimbatore city. These two companies are part of their parent company of the Sakthi Group, with its corporate office functioning at Coimbatore city. These two companies were selected as sample. Due to vast spread of these transportation service providers and difficulties encountered by the researcher in data collection, sample population was restricted to 45 per cent of the total employees (1636) working across Tamil Nadu in these two companies. 297 High level Authorities, 904 Middle, and 435 Low Level Employees In the second phase of data collection 693 well structure questioners were distributed among the sample respondents in the administrative and driver cadre employees. In the final stage of the data collection it was observed that out of 693 questioners distributed only 650 questioners was returned by the sample subjects i.e., 547 administrative employees (middle level) and 102 drivers (low level). Rest of the 44 respondents did not return the questioners distributed even after several times of reminders, these 43 questioners were deducted from the actual sample population of 693. The study constitutes 650 sample population.

Results and Discussion

Demographic distribution of the respondents depicted that 52.30 per cent of sample respondents' are male and rest of the 47.70 per cent were female. Further, it was observed that 47.69 per cent of employees' in logistics service sector are aged between 21-39 years and 47.54 per cent of employees' in logistics service sector are degree holders. The study observed that 29.54 per cent employment of in logistics service sector have gained work experiences of 6 month to 1 year, they were very young to the current job. The maximum salary of the employees surveyed ranged between `10000 to `20000, which is bare minimum for healthy survival of family with three to four members.

TABLE: 1: EMPLOYEES' OVERALL SATISFACTION TOWARDS HR POLICIES AND ORGANISATION FACTORS

Variables	Sum	Mean	Rank	% Satisfied Employees	% Dissatisfied Employees
HRM Factors					
Organisational Fit	1296	1.99	9	39.80	60.20
Remuneration And Recognition System	1468	2.26	3	45.20	54.80
Opportunities for Training and Career Development	1379	2.12	7	42.40	57.60
Challenging Employment Assignments and Opportunities	1396	2.15	5	43.00	57.00
Organisational Factors					
Working Environment	1362	2.10	8	42.00	58.00
Organisational Polices / Culture	1392	2.14	6	42.80	57.20
Communication	1438	2.21	4	44.20	55.80
Leadership Practices and the Team Level Co-Operations	1523	2.34	1	46.80	53.20
Organisational Commitment	1516	2.33	2	46.60	53.40

Source: Primary Data

Overall satisfaction of employees towards the organisation that they are working at present. It has been observed that, majority of the respondents' have opined that they are highly satisfied with leadership practices and the team level co-operations in the organisation. It is ranked in first place with an average of 2.34. Followed by, the employees' have said that they are satisfied with the features such as: Organisational commitment, remuneration and recognition systems. These variables have mean score of 2.33 and 2.26 respectively. Further, the sample respondents' have opined that they are moderately satisfied with the features such as: Peer communication, employment assignments & opportunities and organisational polices / culture. These variables are ranked in fourth, fifth and sixth places with mean score of 2.21, 2.15 and 2.14, correspondingly. On the contrary, the respondents' are

least satisfied with the features such as: Working environment and organisational fit. These variables are ranked in seventh and eighth places with mean score of 2.10 and 1.99, respectively. Employees' satisfaction with the organisation and personal fit is rated at the last place with the lowest mean score of 1.99.

**TABLE: 2: EMPLOYEES' LEVEL OF SATISFACTION
TOWARDS MONETARY AND NON-BENEFITS**

Variables	Sum	Mean	Rank	% Satisfied Employees	% Dissatisfied Employees
Pay Range	1595	2.45	4	49	51
Fringe Benefits	1603	2.47	2	49	51
Job Security	1597	2.46	3	49	51
Social Security Benefits	1880	2.89	1	58	42
HRM practices	1516	2.33	6	47	53
Health Care Benefits	1486	2.29	7	46	54
Insurance	1438	2.21	8	44	56
Other Allowances	1586	2.44	5	49	51

Source: Primary Data

Employees have expressed high degree of satisfaction towards the social security benefits offered in the organisation, it is ranked in first place with an average of 2.89. Followed by, the employees' have said that they are satisfied with the features such as: Fringe benefits, job security and pay range. These variables are ranked in second, third and fourth places with mean score of 2.47, 2.46 and 2.45, respectively. Similarly, the sample respondents' have opined that they are moderately satisfied with the features such as: Other allowances offered and the HRM practices followed. These variables are ranked in fifth and sixth places with mean score of 2.44 and 2.33, correspondingly. Further, the respondents' possess low level of satisfaction towards the features such as: Health care benefits and insurance schemes offered in the organisation.

Structural Equation Modeling Analysis- Goodness-Fit Model

SEM was drafted to measure the association between employees' level of satisfaction towards HRM policies and organisation factors and its influences on their intention of turnover. In the current study HR polices includes: Organisational Fit, Remuneration and Recognition System, Opportunities for Training and Career Development and Challenging Employment Assignments and Opportunities. The Organisation factors included: Working Environment, Organisational Polices / Culture, Communication, Leadership Practices and the Team Level Co-Operations and Organisational Commitment.

TABLE: 3: VARIABLES EXPANSION

ORGFIT	Person-Organisational Fit
REARCS	Remuneration and Recognition System
OPTACD	Opportunities for Training and Career Development
CEJAAO	Challenging Employment Assignments and Opportunities
WORENV	Working Environment
ORGPOC	Organisational Polices / Culture
COMSYS	Communication System
LPATLC	Leadership Practices and the Team Level Co-Operations
ORGCOM	Organisational Commitment
LENSER	Length of Service
MGTCAD	Management Cadre of the Employees'
TURINT	Turnover Intention of the Employees'

TABLE: 4: CHI-SQUARE RESULT AND GOODNESS OF FIT INDICES OF THE PROPOSED MODEL

Fit Indices	Obtained Value	Accepted Thresholds Levels	Acceptable Value
χ^2	2159.613	NA	NA
Scaled χ^2/df	38	<0.05	<0.05
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	.500	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	.026	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)	.284	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	.261	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	.264	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	.152	0=Poor Fit, 1=Good Fit	0-1
Parsimony Comparative Fit Index (PCFI)	.150	0=Poor Fit, 1=Good Fit	0-1
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	.278	0=Poor Fit, 1=Good Fit	0-1
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	.268	0=Poor Fit, 1=Good Fit	0-1
Root Mean Square Approximation Method (RMSEA)	.000	Value less than 0.07	.05 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

Level of Significance : 5 per cent
 Minimization : .000
 Miscellaneous : .312
 Bootstrap : .000
 Total : .312

**EXHIBIT: 1
 STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELLING ANALYSIS**

GOODNESS-FIT MODEL

On the basis of these measurements, the result of the study shows that the proposed model has a reasonable data fit $\chi^2=2159.613$ ($p=.000$), GFI=.500, AGFI=.026, TLI=.284, CFI=.261, NFI=.264, PNFI=.152, PCFI=.150, RFI=.278, IFI=.268, RMSEA=.000).

TABLE: 5
PATH ANALYSIS STRUCTURE
MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD –REGRESSION WEIGHTAGE

Path			Unstandardized Estimates (β)	S.E	C.R	P Value	Relationship
ORGFIT	<---	LENSER	.123	.025	-4.853	.000	significant
REARCS	<---	LENSER	.045	.023	-2.001	.045	significant
OPTACD	<---	LENSER	.021	.024	.867	.386	Insignificant
CEJAAO	<---	LENSER	.052	.023	-2.235	.025	significant
WORENV	<---	LENSER	.059	.028	-2.141	.032	significant
ORGPOC	<---	LENSER	.166	.024	-6.808	.000	significant
COMSYS	<---	LENSER	.136	.027	-4.966	.000	significant
LPATLC	<---	LENSER	.002	.028	-.056	.956	Insignificant
ORGCOM	<---	LENSER	.133	.029	-4.643	.000	significant
ORGFIT	<---	MGTCAD	.134	.065	2.057	.040	significant
REARCS	<---	MGTCAD	.005	.058	.091	.927	Insignificant
OPTACD	<---	MGTCAD	.136	.061	2.240	.025	significant
CEJAAO	<---	MGTCAD	.042	.060	.707	.479	Insignificant
WORENV	<---	MGTCAD	.025	.071	.359	.720	Insignificant
ORGPOC	<---	MGTCAD	.016	.062	-.262	.793	Insignificant
COMSYS	<---	MGTCAD	.346	.070	4.957	.000	significant
LPATLC	<---	MGTCAD	.156	.072	2.152	.031	significant
ORGCOM	<---	MGTCAD	.191	.073	2.613	.009	significant
TURINT	<---	ORGFIT	.030	.027	1.136	.256	Insignificant
TURINT	<---	REARCS	.004	.030	-.120	.904	Insignificant
TURINT	<---	OPTACD	.184	.029	6.391	.000	significant
TURINT	<---	CEJAAO	.158	.029	-5.410	.000	significant
TURINT	<---	WORENV	.046	.025	1.878	.060	Insignificant
TURINT	<---	ORGPOC	.033	.027	1.215	.224	Insignificant
TURINT	<---	COMSYS	.122	.024	5.000	.000	significant
TURINT	<---	LPATLC	.321	.024	13.232	.000	significant
TURINT	<---	ORGCOM	.384	.024	16.224	.000	significant

Level of Significance: 5 Per cent

The measure of co-efficient of variances reveals that, length of service of the employees and their satisfaction towards: organisational fitness ($\beta=.123$, $p=.000$), remuneration and recognition system ($\beta=.045$, $p=.045$), challenging employment assignments and opportunities ($\beta=.052$, $p=.025$), working environment ($\beta=.059$, $p=.032$), organisational polices / culture ($\beta=.166$, $p=.000$), communication system ($\beta=.136$, $p=.000$) and organizational commitment ($\beta=.133$, $p=.000$). The measure of co-efficient of variances also reveals that, management cadre employees and their satisfaction towards organisational fitness ($\beta=.134$, $p=.040$), opportunities for training and career development ($\beta=.136$, $p=.025$), challenging employment assignments and opportunities ($\beta=.052$, $p=.025$), communication system ($\beta=.346$, $p=.000$), leadership practices and the team level co-operation ($\beta=.156$, $p=.031$) and organizational commitment ($\beta=.191$, $p=.009$) were observed to significant, it established close relationship between the variables tested.

Whereas the variables: length of service of the employees and their satisfaction towards opportunities for training and career development ($\beta=.021$, $p=.386$) and employees satisfaction towards leadership practices and the team level co-operations ($\beta=.002$, $p=.956$) does not establish close association between each other. Similarly, management cadre of the employees and their satisfaction towards remuneration and recognition system ($\beta=.005$, $p=.927$), challenging employment assignments and opportunities ($\beta=.042$, $p=.479$), working environment ($\beta=.025$, $p=.720$), organisational polices / culture ($\beta=.016$, $p=.793$),

The study further, observed that turnover intention are closely influenced by their: organisation and personal fit mismatching ($\beta=.030$, $p=.256$), employee's satisfaction towards remuneration and recognition system ($\beta=.040$, $p=.904$), working environment ($\beta=.046$, $p=.060$) and organisation commitment ($\beta=.030$, $p=.224$). The study further observed that employee's intention to stay in an organisation is duly influenced by employee's satisfaction HR policies and organisation factors like: opportunities for training and career development ($\beta=.184$, $p=.000$), challenging employment assignments and opportunities ($\beta=.158$, $p=.000$), communication system ($\beta=.122$, $p=.000$), leadership practices and the team level co-operations ($\beta=.321$, $p=.000$) and organisational commitment ($\beta=.384$, $p=.000$). Based on the statistical inferences it has been concluded that the all four hypotheses stands partially accepted and partially rejected.

Findings and Conclusion

The study findings indicated that majority of the employees surveyed at both ABT and ARC were observed to least satisfied with both HR policies and organisation factors adhered in their organisation. The study further reveals that employees turn over intention is close linked with their dissatisfaction towards: organisation and personal fit, remuneration and recognition system, working environment and poor organisation commitment. Thus, it is suggested to the ABT and ARC parcel service companies to adopt strategic recruitment practices of finding right man for right job and always aim to pay them adequate salary and other perks. These organisations are also suggested to adhere very employee friendly work environment in order to enhance their level of satisfaction and to retain them as committed employees.

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